

Some chemistry of organoarsenic and -antimony compounds[†]

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The interest in organoarsenic and -antimony compounds is being renewed due to their wide ranging applications which include as precursors for chemical vapor deposition of Group III-V semiconductors, versatile ligands and reagents in organic synthesis. The present paper intends to discuss some salient features of the work carried out in author's laboratory on organoarsenic and -antimony compounds. In this paper reactions of $RM(III)$, $R_2M(III)$, $R_3M(V)$ ($M = As, Sb$) species with vanthates and phosphorus based acids are described. Design and development of several tertiary arsines including heterocyclic derivatives as precursors and their reaction chemistry are discussed.

During the last decade or so organometallic chemistry has taken a new turn and activities at its interface with materials science have accelerated exponentially. The continuing drive to scale down dimensions of electronic devices has been a motivating factor for such a turn. Organometallic compounds are now extensively used as molecular precursors in chemical vapor deposition process (MOCVD) and related techniques (photo-MOCVD, plasma-CVD, MOMBE, etc.) to deposit a wide variety of inorganic materials including semiconductors. The success of CVD technique depends on the availability of suitable precursors. The search for better precursor molecules with desirable properties has been a driving force for continued current interest in organometallic chemistry.

Organometallics of group 15 elements has come to an age and find extensive application in the deposition of III-V compound semiconductor materials (eqn. 1)¹⁻⁵.

Thin films of sulfides (As_2S_3 , band gap ≈ 3.6 eV) are used for holographic recording⁶, optical memories⁷, relief imaging⁸, high resolution microlithography⁹, etc. Under these perspectives, we have investigated some chemistry of group 15 elements. Results of our work are described here.

Tertiary arsines

Metallocycloalkanes have been known to give volatile hydrocarbons with clean cleavage of the M-C bond. This prompted us to examine arsacycloalkanes. The reactions of $PhAsCl_2$ with di-Grignard reagent $BrMg(CH_2)_nMgBr$ ($n = 4$ or 5) in THF readily gave phenylarsacycloalkanes $PhAs(CH_2)_n$ ($n = 4$ or 5) as colorless oily liquids which could be distilled in vacuo (Scheme 1). The mass spectra showed molecular ion peaks¹⁰.

Scheme 1

Several palladium and platinum complexes of these arsacycloalkanes were synthesized and characterized. Thermogravimetric analyses of several of these have been carried out to assess whether purification of arsacycloalkanes can be achieved by thermolysis of their adducts. It is evident from the TG curve (Fig. 1) that both the ligands are liberated at $\sim 275^\circ$ leaving palladium chloride.

The molecular structure of $[PdCl_2(PhAsCH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2)_2]$ shows that the Pd atom is in a square-planar environment with the arsacycloalkane ligands in a *trans* arrangement (Fig. 2). The six-membered metallocyclic ' AsC_5 ' ring is puckered and adopts a chair conformation.

The high CF bond energy in perfluoroorganic group may result in clean cleavage of the M-C bond from their organometallic compounds leaving little or no carbon contamination. It has been indeed demonstrated by the Russian workers. Thus it was thought to examine the pentafluorophenyl derivatives of arsenic, antimony and bismuth. They are obtained by the reaction of MCl_3 with C_6F_5MgBr as colorless crystalline solids. The ¹³C NMR spectra (Fig. 3) showed resonances coupled with ¹⁹F nuclei. The C-1 resonance showed metal dependence while other resonances are little affected. The ¹⁹F NMR spectra (Fig. 4) displayed three resonances each showing fluorine couplings. As the mass of the

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Fig. 1. TG curve for $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhAsCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2]$

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram for $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PhAsCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2]$.

Fig. 3. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of $\text{Sb}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3$

metal atom increases deshielding of the *ortho* fluorine resonance also increases¹¹.

Another group of tertiary arsines containing *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine has been designed. They are obtained by the reaction of [2-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenyl]lithium with RASX_2 or Me_2AsI (Scheme 2)¹².

Scheme 2

The mass spectra of Ph derivative showed molecular ion peak while in other cases highest mass peak was attributable to M-R. These compounds were characterized by ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra. The NCH_2 protons for $\text{RAS}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2)_2$ appeared as an AB pattern (Fig. 5). However, when R is Ph, molecule is fluxional, AB pattern could be observed at -40° ¹².

Xanthates, dithiocarbamates and thiophosphate complexes

Complexes of chelating chalcogenolate ligands offer a promising alternative as they can deliver both metal and chalcogenide ligand avoiding mixing problems, significantly more stable and less toxic, non-pyrophoric and easier to handle than their alkyl derivatives. For example, $\text{RM}(\text{E}_2\text{CNET}_2)$ (R = Me, Et; M = Zn, Cd; E = S, Se), $\text{Cd}(\text{S}_2\text{PET}_2)_2$ (for ME), $\text{Et}_2\text{In}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)$ (for In_2S_3), $\text{Ni}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2$, $\text{Co}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEEt}_2)_3$ (for Ni_3S_2 and Co_3S_8 films) have been used to deposit metal sulfide films¹³.

In the light of this the chemistry of organoarsenic(III) and antimony(III) xanthate¹⁴⁻¹⁶, dithiocarbamate¹⁶, mono-^{17,18} and dithiophosphate^{19,20} complexes has been explored (Scheme 3).

These reactions are quite facile and proceed smoothly at room temperature. The resulting products are colorless to pale yellow mobile oils or crystalline solids, soluble in common organic solvents and are monomeric.

The xanthate complexes, $[\text{PhM}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_2]$ (M = As or

Fig. 4. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of $\text{As}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3$.

Sb) tend to decompose on slight heating ($\sim 120^\circ$) to $[\text{PhMS}]$ (eqn. 2) as revealed by TG analysis^{14,15},

The mass spectra of the diorganoarsenic derivatives, $\text{Me}_2\text{As}(\text{S}_2\text{CNMe}_2)$ (m/z 225), $[\text{Me}_2\text{As}\{\text{SOP}(\text{OEt})_2\}]$ (m/z = 274) $[\text{Ph}_2\text{As}\{\text{SOP}(\text{OR})_2\}]$ show molecular ion peaks with the exception to the xanthate derivative, e.g. $[\text{Me}_2\text{As}(\text{S}_2\text{COEt})]$ for which molecular ion peak was not observed.

Scheme 3

The mass spectra of mono-organo complexes (xanthates, dithiocarbamates, mono- and dithiophosphates) show similar behavior. None of the spectra exhibit molecular ion peak indicating pyrolytic decomposition. Two prominent decomposition pathways appear to operate with the loss of metal-alkyl/phenyl group or one of the ligand moieties¹⁴⁻²⁰.

The ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P NMR spectra of all the complexes

Fig. 5. Variable temperature ^1H NMR spectra of $\text{PhAs}(\text{C}_6\text{C}_4\text{CH}_2\text{-NMe}_2)_2$.

exhibit single set of resonances characteristic of metal-alkyl/phenyl group and the ligand fragment. The ^{13}C NMR spectra (Table 1) of the RAs group in the dithiocarbamate complexes is deshielded compared with the corresponding xanthate complexes, consistent with the stronger coordination of the former ligand¹⁶. The ^{31}P NMR data of monothiophos-

Table. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR resonance for the methylarsenic(III) complexes

MeAs(III) complexes	AsMe NMR resonance		Me ₂ As(III) complexes	Me ₂ As NMR resonance	
	^1H	^{13}C		^1H	^{13}C
[MeAs(S ₂ COEt) ₂]	1.93	17.4	[Me ₂ As(S ₂ COEt)]	1.44	13.6
[MeAs(S ₂ CNMe ₂) ₂]	2.05	23.2	[Me ₂ As(S ₂ CNMe ₂)]	1.47	12.4
[MeAs(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂]	2.04	23.2	[Me ₂ As(S ₂ CNEt ₂)]	1.46	12.5
[MeAs{S ₂ P(OEt) ₂ }] ₂	1.98	20.3	[Me ₂ As{S ₂ P(OEt) ₂ }]	1.49	14.8
[MeAs{S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂ }] ₂	2.03	21.3	[Me ₂ As{S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂ }]	1.48	14.7
[MeAs{SOP(OEt) ₂ }] ₂	2.19	21.1	[Me ₂ As{SOP(OEt) ₂ }] ₂	1.56	15.4

phate complexes suggests that they are bonded to arsenic atom through sulfur in a monodentate fashion¹⁷.

The structures of two dithiocarbamate complexes [RAs(S₂CNEt₂)₂] (R = Me or Ph) were established by X-ray diffraction method¹⁶. The arsenic atom forms three close contacts, one with the R group at 1.97 Å and two to sulfur atoms, As–S = 2.323(2)–2.344(2) Å. If these close contacts were considered to define the coordination geometry, i.e. dithiocarbamate ligands are monodentate, then the environment about the arsenic atom would be best described as pyramidal with the lone-pair of electrons being stereochemically active (pyramidal angles vary between 82.76(9) and 98.5(2)° in the two structures). However, the two remaining sulfur atoms are in close proximity to arsenic atom having As...S = 2.84–2.54 Å. These distances are significantly within the sum of the van der Waals radii of arsenic and sulfur of 3.74 Å. If the As–S interactions were considered significant, the coordination geometry would be based on a skewed-trapezoidal pyramidal geometry with one site vacant, i.e. occupied by a lone-pair of electrons¹⁶.

The crystal structures of [PhM{S₂P(OPrⁱ)₂}]₂ (Fig. 6)

 Fig. 6. Structure of [PhM{S₂P(OPrⁱ)₂}]₂

are isomorphous and consist of discrete molecules²⁰. The two dithiophosphate ligands form an approximate basal plane and the phenyl group occupies an axial position in the central atom's square-pyramidal environment. The overall geometry of the central metal atoms is consistent with the

presence of a stereochemically active lone-pair of electrons occupying an axial position, *trans* to the phenyl group, in the octahedral distribution of six electron pairs. The ligands chelate the central metal atom with unequal M–S bonds. The difference between the short and long M–S bonds in Sb of approximately 0.54 Å is significantly less than the difference of approximate 0.8 Å found in As derivative. The geometry of the dithiophosphate ligands in two complexes is similar.

Some chemistry of triorganoarsenic(V) and -antimony (V) with phosphorus based acids has also been investigated as a curious extension of trivalent derivatives. The reactions of ammonium dithiophosphates with triphenylantimony(V) dihalides result into an intramolecular redox process leading to the formation of triphenylstibine and disulfides²¹. However, with strongly electron-withdrawing perfluorophenyl such complexes have been isolated successfully²²

The monothiophosphate complexes are readily prepared by the reaction of triorganoantimony dihalides with ammonium salts of monothiophosphate^{22,23} as colorless oily products. They have been characterized by NMR (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{31}P) data. The ^{31}P NMR spectra exhibit a singlet in the region 55.3–58.6 ppm indicative of O-bonded monothiophosphate ligand. This is further substantiated by the X-ray structural analysis of [Me₃Sb(OSPPH₂)₂]²⁴.

Triorganoarsenic(V) and -antimony(V) diphenylphosphinate complexes have also been studied (Scheme 4)^{22,25,26}.

Scheme 4

The bis-complexes are readily obtained by the reaction of R₃MX₂ with silver diphenylphosphinate as colorless oil (in

case of arsenic) or solids (antimony derivatives)^{22,25,26}. These complexes have been characterized by NMR both solid state and high resolution and mass spectral data. These data suggest that the arsenic compounds are discrete molecular species while the antimony complexes are associated in the solid state (Fig. 7). The ³¹P NMR resonances for

Fig. 7. FAB mass spectrum of $[\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2]$.

the solid samples appeared at higher frequencies than that for the CDCl_3 solution. (For example : $\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2$ δ 21.8 solution, 31.5 solid state; $\text{Et}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2$ δ 21.0 solution, 28.1 solid state (Fig.8); $\text{Pr}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2$ δ 21.6 solution, 27.4 solid state). This change in chemical shift may be interpreted either due to the crystal packing effects or

Fig. 8. Solid state (a) and solution (b) ¹³P NMR spectra of $[\text{Et}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2]$.

due to the different structures in the solid state and solution.

When the reaction of R_3SbBr_2 with silver diphenylphosphinate was carried out in 1 : 1 stoichiometry with the view to isolate $[\text{R}_3\text{SbBr}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)]$, an equilibrium between the bromo, bis- and the dibromide was established instead. Similar equilibria were established when Bu_3SbBr_2 was treated with $\text{Ph}_2\text{PO}_2\text{H}$ in the presence of triethylamine or Bu_3SbBr_2 with $[\text{Bu}_3\text{Sb}(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)_2]$.

Reaction of $\text{Bu}_3^x\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ with $\text{Ph}_2\text{PO}_2\text{H}$ in benzene solution followed by hydrolysis yields hydroxo complexes $[\text{Bu}_3^x\text{Sb}(\text{OH})(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)]$ ($x = n$ or i)²⁶. The IR spectra show broad band at 3325 and 3175 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} absorptions.

The structure of $[\text{Bu}_3^i\text{Sb}(\text{OH})(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)]$ has been determined unambiguously. There are two independent molecules comprising the crystallographic asymmetric unit which are similar to each other. The Sb atom in each molecule exists in a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with the three organic substituents defining the equatorial plane. The axial positions are occupied by the hydroxide group and an O atom derived from a diphenylphosphinate ligand. The Sb-O-P distances are significantly longer than the Sb-OH distances as expected. The diphenylphosphinate ligand coordinates in the monodentate mode as the secondary Sb-O₂ distance (3.94, 3.91 Å) is longer than the sum of the van der Waals radii of 3.78 Å for Sb and O. These oxygen atoms participate in intermolecular associations to symmetry related hydroxide groups. This mode of association leads to the formation of zigzag chains mediated by Sb-OH...O=P hydrogen bonds (Fig. 9), extending along the *b*-direction²⁶.

Fig. 9. Zigzag chains mediated by Sb-OH...O=P hydrogen bond in $[\text{Bu}_3^i\text{Sb}(\text{OH})(\text{O}_2\text{PPh}_2)]$.

A word of caution

Such programs must comply with the state and federal governments legislation on toxic effluents handling and disposal. We are fully aware from the devastating health crisis in Bengal, where high levels of arsenic have leached from natural underground sources (particularly pyrite (iron sulfide) ores) into village wells. Thousands of tube-well wa-

ters have arsenic content well above the World Health Organisation (WHO) permissible limit of 0.01 mg dm^{-3} , with some as high as 4.1 mg dm^{-3} . Symptoms of arsenic poisoning are generalized pigmentation (melanosis) and rough, dry nodular skin (keratosis).

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